

Detection of Factors Affecting Cognitive Function in Environmental Sounds

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ABSTRACT

The detection of environmental sounds that affect our daily life makes it possible to assess the suitability of the surrounding sound environment to the situation. In this study, EEGs of 20 healthy adults were measured and analyzed for changes in the frequency band power and event-related potentials. Consequently, pink noise, which changes its volume periodically, was found to easily reach the primary auditory cortex and induce changes in deep brain functions. In addition, a method for detecting environmental sounds in daily life, including such acoustic elements, is proposed. This method is developed by preparing 10-second samples of each environmental sound corresponding to the categories indicated in the environmental sound dataset ESC-50, except for short-time shot sounds. Periodic volume changes were extracted using autocorrelation analysis, and the presence of pink noisiness was determined using the flatness and crest values of the acoustic property index. Consequently, air conditioning, road repair, and washing machine sound samples were selected as typical environmental sounds containing the applicable sound elements, and all of the selected samples were long-lasting continuous sounds emitted by machines.

1. INTRODUCTION

Humans achieve various purposes in their lives, including ensuring safety, by interpreting information from their surrounding environmental stimuli. By receiving and processing these environmental stimuli appropriately, humans can maintain a comfortable and efficient social life. However, in some cases, exposure to unnecessary or excessive intensity of stimuli interferes with their comfortable life.

Conventional methods of evaluating environmental noise are primarily based on psychological effects, such as “annoyance” and “discomfort,” or epidemiological studies of the effects from the perspective of health damage and prevalence [1–6]. In particular, from the viewpoint of noise, little consideration has been given to the effects of low-level sounds that are not considered harmful to health or that do not cause annoyance or discomfort. In recent years, studies on the mechanism of the effects of

environmental noise on living organisms, such as the relationship with cardiovascular diseases, have been reported. A study suggested the possibility of noise as a cause of acute cardiac impairment, showing that in cases of death at night, the level of noise exposure 2 h prior to death was significantly associated with cardiac-related mortality [7]. However, it is still unclear what characteristics of the sound source cause these effects on the body and mind. The sound quality was evaluated in a study using the variation coefficient of the peak value of the frequency component of respiration [8]. Another study quantified stress during noise exposure by measuring the change in salivary amylase concentration [9]. Numerous studies have examined the effects of sound on the human body, but all of them use sounds that are conventionally defined as noise, and do not consider the effects of sounds that are not loud or unpleasant. In a previous experiment, the authors found that the biological response to continuous sound stimulation changed over time. The amplitude of P50 of electroencephalogram (EEG) event-related potentials (ERPs) gradually declined with each successive presentation of a pure tone of 1000 Hz at the same interval. This suggests that the continuous input of the same tone gradually suppresses the input to the primary auditory cortex [10]. However, as the tone of the stimulus used was a sine wave, the inhibitory effect of this continuous listening might be unique to this tone. In addition, most of the studies investigating the effects of specific tones on the human body have been conducted using musical sounds, and no studies have examined the effects of sound stimuli other than musical sounds on the body using EEG as an indicator [11,12].

If environmental sounds affecting the human body in daily life can be detected, it is possible to evaluate whether the surrounding sound environment is suitable according to the situation. In recent years, there have been many reports on the evaluation of environmental sound recognition methods [13–15]. Most of the reports focus on the recognition of singularly occurring sounds; the recognition method of environmental sounds in the background has rarely been evaluated. Since the sounds that have been pointed out to affect the human body are not singular sounds but sounds with a certain length, it is necessary to consider methods for analyzing sounds with a certain duration when proposing a method for recognizing environmental sounds regarding their effects on the human body.

In this study, to consider environmental sounds that have regular changes in volume and that affect the body, the sound elements and their functioning mechanisms were

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examined by examining the changes in EEG while listening to these sounds. Next, to consider the existence of environmental sounds containing the sound elements that affect human body, an acoustic analysis method was proposed to evaluate the similarity between sounds that affect human body and environmental sounds by using a set of typical environmental sound categories, and the similar environmental sound categories were shown.

2. EFFECTS OF CONTINUOUS AUDITORY STIMULATION ON THE HUMAN BODY

2.1 Methods

2.1.1 Experiment Participants

The experimental participants were 20 healthy adults (15 males and 5 females) aged 20–22 years (mean age: 21 years). The purpose of the study, maintenance of anonymity, and possibility of withdrawal from participation were explained to the participants in document and orally, and informed consent was obtained.

2.1.2 Sound Stimuli and Presentation Methods

The sound stimuli were presented for 2 min and 40 s (± 5 s) for a total of 80 times. This stimulus presentation was defined as one set, and three sets were conducted using three different types of sounds (the type of stimulus sound was the same within each set). The sound types consisted of a pure tone of 1000 Hz (S_s), white noise (S_w), and pink noise (S_p). The length of each tone was 500 ms, and the inter-stimulus interval (ISI) was randomized for each pronunciation between 1.5 and 2.5 s. The sound files were in wav format (44.1 kHz, 16 bits). A presentation software (Superlab 5.0, Cedrus) was used to control the sound presentation. The timing of the sound stimulus is shown in Figure 1. The black area represents the sounding area, and the white area represents the silent area with a random span.

Figure 1. Timing of sound stimuli

The sound stimuli were presented by playing a file on a computer and pronouncing it via an audio interface (UA-55, Roland) with sealed earphones (hf5, ETY MOTIC RESEARCH). The volume of the sounds in the sounding parts were standardized to 60 dB SPL. This volumes was measured using an artificial ear (TYPE2015E, ACO Co.,Ltd.).

2.1.3 EEG Measurement and Analysis

EEG was measured using an electroencephalograph (Nexus10, Mindmedia). Silver-silver chloride electrodes for EEG were placed on the parietal (Cz) and occipital (O1,

O2) of the head according to the 10-20 international system, and reference electrodes were placed on the earlobes. The sampling frequency was 256 Hz.

The ERPs were calculated by averaging the EEG data of the Cz site for the number of times the stimulus was presented. A duration of 1000 ms after the sound was emitted was used to calculate the average. In this study, P50 was used as an index of the intensity of the input to the primary sensory cortex. P50 was defined as the positive peak value in the 30–90 ms of the ERP waves. The values of P50 during sound exposure were compared for each stimulus condition. The power of the alpha2 band was used as an indicator of the level of deep brain activity. The alpha2 band power was calculated as the squared mean value of the EEG at O1 and O2 with a 10–13 Hz bandpass filter. For each stimulus condition, the mean alpha2 band power was calculated for 1 min before and after the stimulus presentation and during the stimulus presentation, and the values of the difference between each section were compared.

2.2 Results

2.2.1 Changes in P50 in ERP

The mean and standard error of the ERP component P50 potentials during the presentation of each sound stimulus is shown in Figure 2. The P50 potential values for each experimental participant were determined to follow a normal distribution, not significant by the Shapiro-Wilk test in any of the stimulus conditions. ANOVA showed that there was no significant difference between the means of the three groups ($\alpha = 0.05$), but multiple comparisons by the Tukey test indicate that the value when hearing SP can be considered relatively high (S_s - S_w : $p=0.85$, S_s - S_p : $p=0.24$, S_w - S_p : $p=0.08$). In addition, Mauchly's test confirmed that sphericity of the data can be assumed.

Figure 2. P50 potential during sound stimuli hearing

2.2.2 Power of alpha2 Band

The statistical values and the results of the t-test for differences of the alpha2 band power between the stimulus presentation period and the period before and after the stimulus for each sound stimulus are shown in Table 1. The values of alpha2 band power in the S_s and S_p presentation

periods were significantly lower than those in the pre- and post-periods ($\alpha = 0.05$).

	Hearing		Before/after hearing		<i>p</i>
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
S_S	7.84	4.67	8.35	4.50	0.041
S_W	8.23	4.85	8.27	4.73	0.876
S_P	7.47	4.41	8.21	5.17	0.015

Table 1 Comparison of alpha2 band power during hearing and before/after hearing

2.3 Discussion

The peak value of P50 reflects the input intensity of the auditory stimulus to the primary sensory cortex and is used as an index of sensory gating. Sensory gating is a filtering mechanism that works on sensory stimuli input from the external environment, which can suppress the input of unnecessary stimuli to the sensory cortex [16, 17]. In this study, the values while hearing S_P were higher than those while hearing other types of sounds. This implies that sensory gating is not easily applied to pink noise with regular volume changes and that the input intensity to the primary auditory cortex of this sound is not easily suppressed.

The EEG alpha2 powers during the presentation of the S_S and S_P stimuli were significantly reduced compared to the values before and after the stimuli. The EEG alpha2 band power is used as an indicator to reflect fundamental brain activity [18]. This result suggests that the continuous presentation of pink noise and pure tones may suppress fundamental brain activity. This may be due to fast auditory cognitive processing of stimuli by S_P , which are difficult to be sensory-gated, and therefore may suppress fundamental brain activity by making it difficult for brain functions to operate multimodally. On the other hand, S_S affected the fundamental brain functions even when sensory gating was applied, owing to the high local spectral density of energy on a single frequency compared to other stimuli.

3. DETECTION OF SOUNDS WITH PHYSIOLOGICAL EFFECTS IN ENVIRONMENTAL SOUNDS

3.1 Environmental Sounds with Repeated Volume Changes

Pink noise with regular volume changes may suppress fundamental brain function. In this section, we discuss the existence of such sounds in daily living spaces by using environmental sounds in typical living spaces. For preparing the environmental sounds to be used, 10 s of sound samples that match the category of environmental sounds lasting more than 10 s each were employed, referring to the categories of the ESC-50 dataset [19], which is widely used for environmental sound classification. The samples were obtained from the BBC Sound Effect library and from the original recordings in a

living environment. The file format of the sample sounds was 44.1 Hz, 16-bit, monaural wav format, and the volume was adjusted to EBU R128 = -24.0 LUFS in all samples.

3.2 Method for Detecting Environmental Sounds that Repeatedly Change in Volume

From the 25 environmental sound samples, those with continuous repeated volume changes were extracted. The period of the repeated volume changes to be extracted was set to be more than 50 ms (less than 20 Hz), which exceeds the audible range.

To detect the repeated volume change, we correlated the self-waveform with the waveform that was shifted by various periods, and obtained the peak value as the maximum value of the correlation in 50 sampling periods (1.13 ms) before and after, and set the top five periods with high correlation as the “basic period”. Then, for each basic period detected, the correlation was calculated with a signal shifted by an integer multiple (up to 10 periods) of the basic period (e.g., 100 ms, 200 ms, 300 ms for 100 ms basic period (10 Hz)) to check whether the basic period is a regular change over the whole signal. If the change in the correlation coefficient with successive shifts from the basic period to 10 times the fundamental period is always greater than 50% of the correlation coefficient at the previous shift, then there is a regular change across the signal during that basic period. Consequently, for 5 of the 25 environmental sounds, there is a regular volume change with 12 basic periods of 2.1–15.9 Hz. An example of the correlation calculation is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. An example of sound regularity judgement

3.3 Method for Detecting Environmental Sounds including Pink Noise

Next, we tested whether the same environmental sound contained pink noise using the following procedure. Flatness and crest [20] were calculated as features of each sound. In the pink noise that was repeatedly sounded at regular intervals (0.2, 0.5, and 1.0 Hz), flatness showed high values and the crest showed low values, as depicted in the values of the sound sample PinkNoise (0.2, 0.5, and 1.0 Hz) in Table 2. The flatness and crest are considered to be effective in determining the pink noise characteristics of sounds. The same report was made for a musical analysis [21].

3.4 Judgment Results of Environmental Sound Samples by the Proposed Analysis Method

Table 2 lists the fundamental frequency of the volume change for the sound sample that had a periodic volume change, among the 25 environmental sound samples. The values of flatness and crest for each sample sound are listed, with values of flatness above 0.75 and crest below 5 shown in bold. The four sound samples with both values in bold are air conditioning, rain, road repairs, and washing machine. These samples are considered to contain pink noise characteristics. Therefore, when combined with the results of the detection of sounds with regular volume changes, among the 25 environmental sound samples, 3 samples were found to exhibit regular volume changes and pink noise characteristics: air conditioning, road repairs, and washing machine.

Category	Regular volume alteration freq. (Hz)	Flatness	Crest	Like pink noise with regular volume change
air conditioning	2.08	0.79	4.02	+
airplane		0.54	4.88	
chainsaw		0.38	6.21	
chirping birds		0.14	45.27	
clock alarm		0.09	190.27	
clock tick		0.46	27.98	
crackling fire		0.85	11.11	
crickets		0.14	28.97	
crying baby		0.26	25.29	
engine		0.57	2.93	
farm machine		0.80	8.86	
frog		0.12	35.76	
hand saw		0.32	12.50	
helicopter		0.34	7.32	
insects		0.11	17.40	
keyboard typing		0.30	17.08	
rain		0.88	3.99	
refrigerator	5.36	0.59	4.09	
	12.07	0.59	4.09	
	2.30	0.59	4.09	
	3.71	0.59	4.09	
	2.84	0.59	4.09	
road repairs	15.90	0.91	3.78	+
sea waves		0.70	5.52	
siren		0.37	7.19	
snoring		0.55	12.77	
train		0.56	5.09	
vacuum cleaner		0.54	8.34	
washing machine	2.64	0.78	4.61	+
	2.20	0.78	4.61	+
	3.30	0.78	4.61	+
	4.40	0.78	4.61	+
PinkNoise (0.2 Hz)	-	0.99	2.46	+
PinkNoise (0.5 Hz)	-	0.97	1.81	+
PinkNoise (1.0 Hz)	-	0.96	1.70	+

Table 2. Analysis results of environmental sound samples

4. SUMMARY

By measuring EEG event-related potentials P50 and α 2-band power during sound stimulation, we confirmed that pink noise with repeated volume changes is more likely to reach the primary sensory cortex and causes changes in deep brain functions than other type of noises. Furthermore, we investigated the detection of environmental sounds containing such acoustic elements to assess

environmental sounds in daily life. By applying an algorithm to determine the presence of periodic volume changes and pink noise, the sound samples of air conditioning, road repairs, and washing machines were selected from the category of typical environmental sounds. All three samples were long-lasting sounds produced by the machines.

Acknowledgments

This work was supported by a JSPS KAKENHI Grant.

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